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NITRIC ACID (HNO_3): STRUCTURE, PROPERTIES, SYNTHESIS AND USE

Bakhshilloyev Nozim Komilovich

Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology
Department of Chemical Technology of Inorganic Substances
Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Shodiyev Azim Ziyodullayevich

Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology
Department of Chemical Technology of Inorganic Substances
Bukhara, Uzbekistan

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The nitric acid It is an inorganic compound consisting of nitrogen oxo acid. It is a strong acid, although its pKa (-1.4) is similar to the pKa (-1.74) of the hydronium ion. From this point on, it may be the "weakest" of the many known strong acids.

Its appearance consists of a colorless liquid, which turns yellowish in storage due to the formation of nitrogen gases. Its chemical formula is HNO_3 . It is used in the production of inorganic and organic nitrates, as well as nitroso compounds used in the production of fertilizers, explosives, dye intermediates and various organic chemical compounds.

This acid was already known to alchemists of the 8th century, who called it "agua fortis". The German chemist Johann Rudolph Glauber (1648) developed a method of preparing potassium nitrate by heating it with sulfuric acid.

It is prepared in industry according to the method developed by Wilhelm Oswald (1901). The method, in general, consists of the catalytic oxidation of ammonia, successively producing nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide, forming nitric acid.

In the atmosphere, NO_2 reacts with water in anthropogenic clouds to form HNO_3 . Then, during acid rain, it sinks with water droplets, for example, engulfing sculptures in public squares. The structure of the HNO_3 molecule with the spheres and lattice model shown. The nitrogen atom, a blue sphere, is centered and surrounded by a triangular planar geometry; however, the triangle is broken by one of the longest peaks.

Then the nitric acid molecules are flat. N = O, N-O and N-OH bonds form the vertices of an equilateral triangle. If you look closely, the N-OH bond is elongated compared to the other two (here the white sphere representing the H atom is found

Resonance structures

There are two bonds of the same length: N = O and N-O. This fact contradicts the valence bond theory, where double bonds are predicted to be shorter than single bonds. The explanation for this lies in the phenomenon of resonance, as can be seen in the figure below. Both bonds, N = O and N-O, are resonance equivalent. This structure model is graphically represented using a dashed line between two O atoms (see structure).

When HNO is deprotonated³, the stable anion nitrate NO₃⁻ is formed. In it, the resonance now covers all three O atoms, so HNO₃ has a high Bronsted-Lowry acidity (the ion donor species is H⁺

Physical properties: colorless; pungent smell; liquid; density 1.5 g/cm³; - crystallizes at 41 °C; soluble in water.

Do not smell! Don't try it! Do not allow it to be seen! Do not allow it to fall on the skin! Do not spill! Rules to be followed when working with acid Corrosive to skin, fabric, paper, wood Causes burns to the mucous membrane

Chemical properties Nitric acid is a strong monobasic acid. It is completely dissociated in diluted solutions:

physical and chemical properties

Nitric acid is unstable. It decomposes under the influence of light and heat. A gas called "fox tail" is formed.

Nitric acid, like other acids, gives general reactions characteristic of acids:

The effect of nitric acid on metals is different from other acids. Depending on the concentration of the acid and the activity of the metal, nitric acid is reduced as follows:

Nitric acid reacts differently with metals depending on the concentration of the acid and the temperature:

A mixture of 1 mol of nitric acid and 3 mol of hydrochloric acid is called "salt water". Dice water is a very strong oxidizer, it can dissolve even very passive metals - gold and platinum:

Areas of use

Nitric acid ranks after H_2SO_4 among mineral acids in terms of production and use. Concentrated nitric acid is a colorless dark liquid with a density of 1.52 g/cm³. The freezing point is -410 C, the boiling point is +860 C. HNO_3 forms various hydrates with water. This process is accompanied by the release of heat. HNO_3 has the ability to dissolve and oxidize other metals such as gold, platinum, radium, iridium. Two types of HNO_3 are used in industry. Diluted acid with a concentration of 50-60% is used for the production of fertilizers. Concentrated HNO_3 is used in the production of dyes, varnishes, plastics, textiles, film, and explosives. Until 1920, nitric acid was obtained on the basis of sodium nitrite.

List of references:

1. Фатиллоев, Шамшод Файзулло Угли, Бехзод Мавлон Угли Аслонов, and Алишер Камилевич Ниёзов. "ИЗУЧЕНИЕ МЕХАНИЧЕСКИХ СВОЙСТВ КОЖИ ОБРАБОТАННЫМИ ПОЛИМЕРНЫМИ КОМПОЗИЦИЯМИ." *Universum: технические науки* 11-4 (80) (2020): 49-51.
2. Kazakovich, Khayrullayev Chorikul, Fatilloyev Shamshod Fayzullo o'g'li, Dehkonova Nargiza, and Jabborova Aziza. "STUDY OF THE POSSIBILITY OF USE OF LOCAL PHOSPHORITES AND SEMI-PRODUCTS OF THE PRODUCTION OF COMPOUND FERTILIZERS AS ADDITIVE TO AMMONIA NITRETE." *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)* 7, no. 4 (2022): 49-52.
3. Фатиллоев, Ш. Ф., Ш. Б. Мажидова, and Ч. К. Хайруллаев. "ВЛИЯНИЕ ДОБАВОК АЗОТНОКИСЛОТНОГО РАЗЛОЖЕНИЯ ФОСФОРИТОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОГО КЫЗИЛКУМА НА ГИГРОСКОПИЧЕСКИЕ СВОЙСТВА АММИАЧНОЙ СЕЛИТРЫ." *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 22 (2022): 553-556.
4. Niyozov Sobir Ahror o'g'li, Fatilloyev Shamshod Fayzullo o'g'li, & Bafoev Abduhamid Hoshim o'g'li. (2022). Non-Ferrous Metals and Their Alloys New Innovative Technologies in Production of Non-Ferrous Metals. *Neo Science Peer Reviewed Journal*, 3, 11-20. Retrieved from <https://www.neojournals.com/index.php/nsprj/article/view/31>
5. Ibragimov G.I., Erkayev A.U., Yakubov R.Ya., Turobjonov S.M. Kaliy Xlorid texnologiyasi Dehqonobod kaliyli o'g'itlar zavodi ishchilari va noorganik moddalar texnologiyasi mutaxassisligi bo'yicha ta'lim olayotgan bakalavr va magistrlar uchun uslubiy qo'llanma
6. Amonovich, M. R., Fayzullo o'g'li, F. S., & Mavlon o'g'li, A. B. (2023). Analysis of the Composition of Sludge Waste Released in the Process of

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Potassium Chloride Production from Silvinite Ore. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES, 2(9), 40–42. Retrieved from <https://inter-publishing.com/index.php/IJHSMS/article/view/2507C>

